

Method Development and Validation for the Simultaneous Estimation of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride By Using RP HPLC In Its Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Form

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ABSTRACT

A simple, Accurate, precise method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of the Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride in Tablet dosage form. Retention time of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride were found to be 2.2min and 4.0min. %RSD of the Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride were and found to be 0.97 and 0.50 respectively. %Recover was Obtained as 100.08% and 101.16% for Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride respectively. LOD, LOQ values are obtained from regression equations of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride were 0.10ppm, 0.34ppm and 0.29ppm, 1.04ppm respectively. Regression equation of Esomeprazole is $y = 10568x + 307.3$, and of Levosulpiride is $y = 11649.x + 1207$. Retention times are decreased and that run time was decreased so the method developed was simple and economical that can be adopted in regular Quality control test in Industries.

Keywords: Esomeprazole, Levosulpiride, Accurate, precise, Tablet dosage form

INTRODUCTION

A drug includes all medicines intended for internal or external use for or in the diagnosis, treatment, mitigation or prevention of disease or disorder in human beings or animals, and manufactured exclusively in accordance with the formulae mentioned in authoritative books. (1) Pharmaceutical analysis is a branch of chemistry involving a process of identification, determination, quantification, purification and separation of components in a mixture or determination of chemical structure of compounds. There are two main types of analysis – Qualitative and Quantitative analysis. Qualitative analysis is performed to establish composition of a substance. It is done to determine the presence of a compound or substance in a given sample or not. The

various qualitative tests are detection of evolved gas, limit tests, color change reactions, determination of melting point and boiling point, mass spectroscopy, determination of nuclear half-life etc. Quantitative analysis techniques are mainly used to determine the amount or concentration of analyte in a sample and expressed as a numerical value in appropriate units. These techniques are based on suitable chemical reaction and either measuring the amount of reagent added to complete the reaction or measuring the amount of reaction product obtained the characteristic movement of a substance through a defined medium under controlled conditions, electrical measurement or measurement of spectroscopic properties of the compound. (2)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Reagent	Specifications
Potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate (Merck – HPLC grade)	Mol. Formula – KH_2PO_4 Mol. Weight – 136.09
Orthophosphoric acid (Merck – HPLC grade)	Mol. Formula – H_3PO_4 Mol. Weight – 98
Ammonium acetate (Merck-GR)	Mol. Formula- $\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ Mol. Weight-77.0825
Methanol (Merck hplc grade)	Mol. Formula – CH_3OH Mol. Weight – 32.04
Acetonitrile (Merck – HPLC grade)	Mol. Formula – CH_3CN Mol. Weight – 41.05
Water	Milli Q Grade

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METHODS

Preparation of buffer (0.01N KH₂PO₄)

Accurately weighed 1.36gm of potassium dihydrogen Ortho phosphate in a 1000ml of Volumetric flask add about 900ml of milli-Q water and degas in a sonicator and finally make up the volume with water and pH adjusted to 5.4 with dil. OPA

Standard Preparation:

Accurately Weighed and transferred 15mg of levosulpiride and 8mg of Esomeprazole working Standards into a 10ml clean dry volumetric flask, add 3/4th volume of diluent, sonicated for 5 minutes and make up to the final volume with diluents. 1ml from the above two stock solutions was taken into a 10ml volumetric flask and made up to 10ml.

Sample Preparation:

5 tablets were weighed and powdered and transferred into a 50mL volumetric flask, 35mL of diluent added and sonicated for 25 min, further the volume made up with diluent and filtered. From the filtered solution 0.2 ml was pipeted out into a 10 ml volumetric flask and made upto 10ml with diluent.

Linearity:

Linearity solutions are prepared such that 0.25ml, 0.5ml, 0.75ml, 1ml, 1.25ml, 1.5ml from the Stock solutions of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride are taken in to 6 different volumetric flasks and diluted to 10ml with diluents to get 20ppm, 40ppm, 60ppm, 80ppm, 100ppm, 120ppm of Esomeprazole and 37.5ppm, 75ppm, 112.5ppm, 150ppm, 187.5ppm, 225ppm of Levosulpiride.

Standard Preparation:

Accurately Weighed and transferred 15mg of levosulpiride and 8mg of Esomeprazole working Standards into a 10ml clean dry volumetric flask, add 3/4th volume of diluent, sonicated for 5 minutes and make up to the final volume with diluents. 1ml from the above two stock solutions was taken into a 10ml volumetric flask and made up to 10ml.

Sample Preparation:

5 tablets were weighed and powdered and transferred into a 50mL volumetric flask, 35mL of diluent added and sonicated for 25 min, further the volume made up with diluent and filtered. From the filtered solution 0.2 ml was pipeted out into a 10 ml volumetric flask and made upto 10ml with diluent.

Accuracy

Standard Preparation:

Accurately Weighed and transferred 15mg of levosulpiride and 8mg of Esomeprazole working Standards into a 10ml clean dry volumetric flask, add 3/4th volume of diluent, sonicated for 5 minutes and make up to the final volume with diluents. 1ml from the above two stock solutions was taken into a 10ml volumetric flask and made up to 10ml.

Sample preparation

50%: 5 tablets were weighed and calculate the average weight of each tablet then 750mg tablet powder was transferred into a 50mL volumetric flask, 30mL of diluent added and sonicated for 25 min, further the volume made up with diluent and filtered. From the filtered solution 0.2ml was pipeted out into a 10 ml volumetric flask and made up to 10ml with diluent.

100%: 5 tablets were weighed and calculate the average weight of each tablet then 1500mg tablet powder was transferred into a 50mL volumetric flask, 30mL of diluent added and sonicated for 25 min, further the volume made up with diluent and filtered. From the filtered solution 0.2ml was pipeted out into a 10 ml volumetric flask and made up to 10ml with diluent.

150%: 5 tablets were weighed and calculate the average weight of each tablet then 2250mg tablet powder was transferred into a 50mL volumetric flask, 30mL of diluent added and sonicated for 25 min, further the volume made up with diluent and filtered. From the filtered solution 0.2ml was pipeted out into a 10 ml volumetric flask and made up to 10ml with diluent.

Method Development

Many trials were done by changing columns and Mobile phases and were reported below.

This trial was run through ods 250 column with mobile phase composition of 55:45 Buffer and Acetonitrile, Flow rate set at 1ml/min.

Trial 1

Fig. 1 Trial chromatogram 1 Observation: resolution is not good

Trial 2

This trial was run through ODS 250mm column with mobile phase composition of 50:50 A water and Acetonitrile, Flow rate set at 1ml/min.

Fig. 2 Trial chromatogram 2 Observation: Esomeprazole eluted in void range.

Trial 3

This trial was run through ODS 250mm column with mobile phase composition of 40:60 A water and Acetonitrile, Flow rate set at 1ml/min.

Fig. 3 Trial chromatogram 3 Observation: Esomeprazole eluted in void range.

Optimized Method: Drugs were eluted with good retention time, resolution; all the system suitable

parameters like Plate count and Tailing factor were within the limits.

Mobile phase: Buffer and Acetonitrile taken in the ratio 32B:68A

Chromatographic conditions:

Flow rate: 1ml/min

Column: ODS 150mm x 4.6 mm, 5 μ .

Detector wave length: 290nm

Column temperature: 30°C

Injection volume: 10 μ L

Run time: 7min

Diluent: water: methanol 50:50

Fig .4 Optimized chromatogram of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

All the system suitability parameters are within range and satisfactory as per ICH guidelines.

1. System suitability

Table: 1 System suitability studies of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride method

Property	Esomeprazole	Levosulpiride
Retention time (tR)	2.21 ± 0.3 min	4.01 ± 0.3min
Theoretical plates (N)	2641 ± 163.48	4414 ± 163.48
Tailing factor (T)	1.45 ± 0.117	1.36 ± 0.117

Fig: 5 Chromatogram of blank

Fig: 6 Typical chromatogram of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride.

2. Linearity

Six Linear concentrations of Esomeprazole(20-120ppm) and Levosulpiride (37.5ppm to 225ppm) are

prepared and Injected. Regression equation of the the Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride are found to be, $y = 10568x + 307.3$, $y = 11649.x + 120.7$ And regression co-efficient was 0.999.

Table: .2 Calibration data of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride method

S. No.	Concentration Esomeprazole (µg/ml)	Response	Concentration Levosulpiride (µg/ml)	Response
1	0	0	0	0
2	20	219743	37.5	436194
3	40	420301	75	891483
4	60	632028	112.5	1323196
5	80	839036	150	1697713
6	100	1049902	187.5	2202932
7	120	1279655	225	2630631

Fig: 7 Calibration curve of Esomeprazole

Fig: 8 Calibration curve of Levosulpiride

Fig: 9 Linearity 25% Chromatogram of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride method.

Fig: 6.6 Linearity 50% Chromatogram of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride method.

Fig: 6.7 Linearity 75% Chromatogram of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride method.

Fig: 10 Linearity 100% Chromatogram of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride method.

Fig: 11 Linearity 125% Chromatogram of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride method.

Fig: 12 Linearity 150% Chromatogram of Eesomeprazole and Levosulpiride method.

3. Precision:

Eesomeprazole and evosulpiride were found to be 1.3% and 0.1% respectively.

Intraday precision (Repeatability): Intraday

Precision was performed and % RSD for

Table: 3 Repeatability results for Eesomeprazole and Levosulpiride.

Sr. No.	Eesomeprazole	Levosulpiride
1	814986	1754081
2	825795	1754437
3	840851	1758333
4	819155	1752184
5	822084	1752359
6	839797	1754366
Mean	827111	1754293
Std. Dev.	10835.5	2217.2
%RSD	1.3	0.1

*Average of six determinations

Fig: 13 Repeatability Chromatogram of Eesomeprazole and Levosulpiride method.

Inter day precision

Inter day precision was performed with 24 hrs time lag and the %RSD Obtained for Eesomeprazole and Levosulpiride were 1.0% and 0.5%.

Table 4 Inter day precision results for Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride

Sr. No.	Esomeprazole	Levosulpiride
1	834986	1743927
2	843663	1732187
3	830708	1728243
4	848290	1726706
5	832084	1720428
6	848665	1739622
Mean	839732.7	1731852
Std. Dev.	8135.6	8675.3
%RSD	1.0	0.5

Fig: 14 Inter Day precision Chromatogram of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride method

4. **Accuracy:** Three concentrations 50%, 100%, 150%, were injected in a triplicate manner and amount Recovered and % Recovery were displayed in Table 6.5.

Table: 5 Accuracy results of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride

Sample	Amount added (µg/ml)	Amount Recovered (µg/ml)	Recovery (%)	% RSD
Esomeprazole	40	39.04	99.97	0.2
	80	79.82	99.99	0.48
	120	120.99	100.32	0.71
Levosulpiride	75	75.72	100.250	0.79
	150	150.15	101.58	0.33
	225	225.55	101.48	0.18

Fig: 15 Accuracy 50% Chromatogram of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride method.

Fig: 16 Accuracy 100% Chromatogram of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride method.

Fig: 17 Accuracy 150% Chromatogram of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride method.

5. LOD

The parameter LOD was determined by analysis of sample with known concentration of analyte and by establishing the minimum level at which the analyte can be reliably detected. LOD for Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride were found to be 0.10 and 1.04 respectively.

Fig: 6.16 LOD Chromatogram of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride method.

6. LOQ

The parameter LOD was determined by analysis of sample with known concentration of analyte and by establishing the minimum level at which the analyte can be quantified with acceptable accuracy and precision. LOQ for Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride were found to be 0.29 and 1.04 respectively.

Fig: 6.17 LOQ Chromatogram of of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride method.

7. Robustness

Small deliberate changes in method like Flow rate, mobile phase ratio, and temperature are made but there were no recognized change in the result and are within range as per ICH Guide lines.

Table .6 Robustness data of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride method.

S.NO	Robustness condition	Esomeprazole %RSD	Levosulpiride %RSD
1	Flow minus	0.4	1.0
2	Flow Plus	0.4	0.4
3	Mobile phase minus	0.1	0.0
4	Mobile phase Plus	0.1	0.1
5	Temperature minus	0.2	0.5
6	Temperature Plus	0.3	0.5

Fig: 18 Flow minus Chromatogram of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride method.

Fig: 19 Flow plus Chromatogram of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride method.

Fig: 20 Mobile phase minus Chromatogram of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride method.

Fig: 21 Mobile phase Plus Chromatogram of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride method.

Fig: 22 Temperature minus Chromatogram of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride method.

Fig:23 Temperature Plus Chromatogram of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride method.

Assay

Standard preparations are made from the API and Sample Preparations are from Formulation. Both sample and standards are injected six homogeneous

samples. Drug in the formulation was estimated by taking the standard as the reference. The Average %Assay was calculated and found to be 100.08% and 101.16% for Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride respectively.

Table 7 Assay of Tablet

S. No.	Esomeprazole %Assay	Levosulpiride %Assay
1	99.51463	101.865
2	100.5488	101.1793
3	99.00477	100.9489
4	101.1002	100.8591

5	99.16876	100.4924
6	101.1449	101.6136
AVG	100.08	101.16
STDEV	0.97	0.51
%RSD	0.97	0.50

Fig: 24 Assay of Tablet

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Table.8 Summary Table:

Parameters	Esomeprazole	Levosulpiride
Calibration range (mcg / ml)	20-120ppm	37.5-225ppm
Optimized wavelength	290nm	290nm
Retention time	2.2min	4.0min
Regression equation (Y*)	$y = 10568.x + 307.3$	$y = 11649.x + 1207$
Correlation coefficient(r2)	0.999	0.999
Precision (% RSD*)	0.97	0.50
% Recoverv	100.08%	101.16%
Limit of Detection (mcg / ml)	0.10ppm	0.34ppm
Limit of Quantitation (mcg /	0.29ppm	1.04ppm

CONCLUSION

A simple, Accurate, precise method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of the Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride in Tablet dosage form. Retention time of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride were found to be 2.2min and 4.0min. %RSD of the Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride were and found to be 0.97 and 0.50 respectively. %Recoverv was Obtained as 100.08% and 101.16% for Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride respectively. LOD, LOQ values are obtained from regression equations of Esomeprazole and Levosulpiride were 0.10ppm, 0.34ppm and 0.29ppm, 1.04ppm respectively. Regression equation of Esomeprazole is $y = 10568x + 307.3$, and of Levosulpiride is $y = 11649.x + 1207$. Retention times are decreased and that run time was decreased so the method developed was simple and economical that

can be adopted in regular Quality control test in Industries.

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